

Breaking Cost Barriers: How Can Indian Public Giants Lead The International Green Hydrogen Exports

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1. Introduction and Motivation

India’s National Green Hydrogen Mission targets an annual production capacity of 5 million tonnes by 2030, marking a pivotal opportunity to position the country as a leading green energy exporter. However, the challenge lies in achieving cost parity with grey hydrogen and driving the Levelized Cost of green Hydrogen (LCOH) below \$1/kg of hydrogen (Curcio, 2025). This study focuses on Reliance Industries Limited (RIL), a first mover in the green hydrogen domain, to explore how an emerging-country multinational enterprises (EMNE) can evolve from a fossil-fuel-based enterprise into a green hydrogen export leader.

2. Literature Review and Research Gaps

Prior research on EMNE competitiveness (Awate et al., 2012; Momaya, 2019) and corporate transformation (Hansen & Nohria, 2004) provides foundational insights into catch-up strategies and organizational renewal. Yet, there remains limited empirical work applying competitiveness frameworks to deep-tech sustainability segments such as green hydrogen, particularly within the Indian context. This study addresses that gap by integrating theories of competitiveness with strategic management tools including the VRIO framework, Root Cause Analysis, and Scenario Planning, thereby enabling a deeper understanding of how Indian industrial giants can bridge the competitiveness divide in the global energy transition.

3. Methodology

A multi-method qualitative case study approach was followed. Quick benchmarking (QBM) was employed to evaluate RIL’s historical performance. Benchmark firms included peers such as Adani Green and global leaders including Nel ASA, ITM Power, and Thyssenkrupp. This was followed by Problem Structuring Methodology (PSM) that helped identify structural reasons behind RIL’s high hydrogen production costs. The VRIO framework was utilized to evaluate the value, rarity, inimitability, and organizational deployment of RIL’s resources on a quantitative scale, revealing areas of both sustained and temporary advantage. Porter’s Value Chain analysis further. Finally, scenario planning was applied to evaluate strategic options available.

4. Analysis & Findings

QBM reveals RIL’s robust financial position, with a 15% CAGR in revenues (FY2017-FY2023). Substantial forex earnings of ₹1.63 lakh crore underscore global integration. Moreover RIL’s vertically integrated ecosystem provides significant cost advantages. However, R&D intensity (0.5% of revenue), remains far below the typical global range of 5–10%. VRIO analysis reveals RIL’s enduring strengths in its integrated infrastructure, project execution capabilities, and financial capital base. Critical assets (e.g., Jamnagar complex) offer unmatched platform for optimized scale-ups. However, absence of proprietary electrolyser intellectual property constrains sustainability of competitive advantage. Partnerships, such as the one with Nel ASA (Norway) represent redressal attempts.

5. Conclusion

This study concludes that India’s green hydrogen leadership challenge is primarily technological rather than financial. RIL possesses unmatched capital, infrastructure, and integration capabilities, yet sustained competitiveness will depend on building indigenous electrolyser technology and strategic international linkages. The findings have significant implications at managerial, policy, and strategic levels. From a managerial perspective, RIL must accelerate technology acquisition through mergers, acquisitions, and joint ventures. Leveraging the Jamnagar ecosystem will be essential to achieve economies of scale. Additionally, forming a dedicated global green hydrogen business unit focused on localized R&D could facilitate technological self-reliance and innovation speed.